

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 1.5 to AD4.1 – Information Leaflet for Children

WP 4

Co-funded by
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Project approved by *[specify name of the committee]* with ref. n° XXXXX

PARC TASK 4.1 TEMPLATE

INFORMATION LEAFLET FOR CHILDREN

[title of study, e.g. PARC aligned study on [specify name of pollutant(s)]

INSTRUCTIONS ON HOW TO USE THIS TEMPLATE

This document is a template, which can be used to develop an assent form for children participants in PARC surveys, if demanded by the study design and national requirements. You may introduce changes, to meet those requirements. To use this template, adjust the text as you find appropriate for your study.

The PARC templates for children are:

"CH_IL – Information leaflet": Information Leaflet for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_QA – Questions and Answers": Questions and Answers for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_AF – Assent form": Assent form for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_FS – Fact Sheet": Fact sheet on chemicals for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"ADOL-CH_CIC - Consent Form Parent or Legal Guardian": "Adjusted Consent Form for Parents / Legal Guardians of Young Participants".

Information Leaflet for Children Participants

**Do you want to help children in Europe to live in a healthy environment?
You can, by taking part in our research study!**

PARC wants to learn about chemicals in the bodies of children who live in Europe and to think of find ways to lower these chemicals in our environment to keep us healthy.

Together, we make the team of PARC!

Our team includes many scientists and families all over Europe.

We are inviting you come along too, by joining our research study.

A research study means learning about something or finding out something new!

There are a lot of *chemicals* present in *nature*, and in all the places where we stay and live, this is called our environment.

Did you know that our bodies, the food we eat, the water we drink and the products we use every day, like our clothes, phones, furniture and toys, are made of chemicals?

We surely need all these chemicals to grow, stay healthy, be productive and enjoy life!

But sometimes, food, air, water and products may be polluted by other chemicals, which have the ability to cause damage to people and the environment. These chemicals are called '*hazardous*' and they are a type of *environmental pollutant*.

PARC wants to stop hazardous chemicals from polluting our environment!

A hazardous chemical can hurt us *only if* enough amount of it gets inside our body and manages to change the way it works. It may take many, many years of being exposed to a hazardous chemical before it manages to cause health problems.

The *good news* is that by learning more about these hazardous chemicals, we can take actions to safeguard against them! *You can help*, by becoming one of **[hundreds]** of children of your age across Europe who are also helping us so we can reach this goal!

PARC wants to help us keep dangerous chemicals out of our environment and our bodies, so that we can stay healthy!

But first, our scientists must find out what is in our bodies

Could you ever imagine that just by giving us a little bit of **[hair, pee]**, scientists can tell you what is in your body? That is all we ask you **[and your mom or dad]**!

Do you want to help us? If you don't, that is OK!

You don't have to join our study if you don't want to! If you decide to take part and later change your mind, you can leave the study at any point. Nobody will mind.

If you help us, we will be able to know how much of certain chemicals children in Europe have in their bodies and to learn where it came from so that we can find ways to lower these chemicals in our environment. That way, you can help us protect both the environment and all children's health.

We would be happy to have you and your family in our PARC team. Please come along and ask us any questions you like or are interested in about our study! **[To get you started, we have created a 'Questions and Answers' leaflet. Please read it together with your mom or dad. You can also learn about the chemicals our scientists want to study, if you want to, by reading another leaflet].**

Thank you for reading this leaflet and for considering to join the PARC study!

Visit our website to find out more! www.eu-parc.eu

This template was adapted from the HBM4EU document available at www.hbm4eu.eu